

ISic1242

I.Sicily inscription 1242

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Messina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140727

1. Θεοῖς Κατα[χθονίοις].
2. Φαβία Μελ [— — — —]
3. ἔζησεν ἔ [τη — — — —]
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492845

EDCS 39101607

PHI 140727

Bibliography

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